

INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF MID DAY MEAL SCHEME IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION: A CASE STUDY OF PURBA MEDINIPUR DISTRICT

Dr. Nizamuddin Ahmed (Corresponding Author)

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Haldia Govt. College, Purba Medinipur
West Bengal, India

Dr. Pijush Kanti Tripathi

Associate Professor, P.G. Department of Geography, Haldia Govt. College, Purba Medinipur,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

This study presents an in-depth analysis of the current situation of elementary education in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal, India, focusing on infrastructural progress and persistent challenges, along with a specific focus on the implementation of the cooked mid-day meal programme. The data were gathered through structured interviews with school heads, direct observations, and interactions with students and Self-Help Group (SHG) members involved in cooked mid-day meal preparation. The study reveals that while many schools meet basic educational standards, critical gaps are present in areas such as sanitation, safety, and essential educational resources, including libraries and playgrounds. Moreover, the cooked mid-day meal programme has shown positive outcomes in enhancing attendance and nutritional support, yet it faces challenges in maintaining hygiene and safe cooking practices. These findings underscore the need for focused improvements and policy-driven interventions to create a more inclusive, supportive and secure learning environment in Purba Medinipur, which is essential for the holistic development of learners of the elementary level of education in this region.

Keywords: Elementary Education, Infrastructures, Educational Resources, and Cooked Mid-Day Meal.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental right and a cornerstone for individual and societal development. In India, the elementary education system plays a crucial role in shaping the future of young learners, providing them with the foundational skills necessary for personal growth and societal participation. Education is not only considered essential for the pleasant development of one's personality but also for the growth and progression of the country as a whole. The elementary level of education shapes the basic foundation of children and is the most important stage among all levels of education. All educationists and policy-makers emphasize elementary education more as it is regarded as the foundation for the growth of not only individuals but also the welfare of the entire nation across the globe. Elementary education in India is regarded as the foundation of compulsory schooling, which is considered essential for individuals. Empirical studies also point out that investment in elementary education increases the output in all the

sectors of the economy much more than other levels of education and that economic returns to investment in primary education are greater than those arising from different levels of education (Colclough, 1980). Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) is still a distant prospect in a substantial part of the world. In India, the central government, the state governments, and other organizations have been involved in the progression of elementary education. The 86th Constitutional Amendment in 2002 made education the fundamental right of children within the age group of six to fourteen years. The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, commonly known as the Right to Education Act (RTE), 2009 was recognized, it stated all children should be made the provision of free education up to the age of fourteen years and for children with special needs up to the age of eighteen years. To ensure the Universalization of Elementary Education, the Government of India has taken several initiatives since its independence; those are Operation Black Board in 1987-1988, the District Primary Education Programme (DPEP) in 1994, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) in 2000-2001, Mid-Day Meal scheme in 1995. After taking several initiatives from the government end, it is vital to analyze from time to time, the necessary areas to make teaching-learning efficient for the children as the teaching-learning processes are of utmost significance for getting quality elementary education to any county's children. Classrooms are considered to be one of the important areas, where learning takes place. It is important to make the students feel comfortable within the classrooms so that their learning and understanding effectively take place. In this context, we may cite one of the unforgettable statements made by Daulat Singh Kothari in his Report i.e. in the Indian Education Commission (1964-1966), where he said, "The Destiny of India is now being shaped in Her Classroom." The Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal presents a unique context for exploring the effectiveness and reach of educational facilities, particularly in the realm of infrastructural support and nutritional programmes such as the mid-day meal initiative.

This study aims to investigate the various facilities offered by schools to their learners, assessing the progress of infrastructural development at the elementary education level. It also seeks to delve into the implementation and impact of the cooked mid-day meal programme, which is designed to enhance student attendance, nutritional status, and overall learning outcomes. By evaluating these dimensions, the research intends to provide a comprehensive overview of the current educational landscape in Purba Medinipur of West Bengal, India identifying both strengths and areas for improvement.

In light of the ongoing challenges faced by the education system, including disparities in access and quality, this study contributes valuable insights into the effectiveness of existing policies and programs. The findings will not only inform stakeholders about the current state of elementary education in the region but also pave the way for future enhancements that can benefit learners across the district.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present study are:

- To understand the various facilities provided by school authorities to their learners at the elementary level of education in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal.

- To enquire about the progress of different infrastructural facilities at the elementary level of education in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal.
- To enquire about the different matters relating to the cooked mid-day meal programme at the institution level of elementary education in Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

- **Elementary Education:** In this present study elementary level of education is the education level from the Class- I standard to Class- VIII standard.
- **Primary School:** In this present study Primary Schools are those schools consisting of Class- I to Class- IV or V.
- **Upper Primary School:** In this present study Upper-Primary Schools are those schools consisting of Class- VI to Class- VIII in ambience of Secondary or Higher Secondary set-up.
- **Cooked Mid Day Meal Programme:** The Cooked Mid-Day Meal Programme, a Scheme, is an initiative of the Government of India aimed at improving the nutritional status of school-age children (0-14 years) across the country through the provision of cooked meals in schools. By 2002, the said programme was put into action in every state in India based on the directives from the Supreme Court of India. The scheme has been renamed the PM-POSHAN (*Pradhan Mantri Poshan Shakti Nirman*) Scheme since September 2021.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is a survey research taking a specific district as the case study area. This study is designed to know the different facilities provided by the Schools to their learners, along with how far the institutions progress in different infrastructural facilities at the elementary level of education and to enquire about the different matters relating to cooked mid-day meal programme at institution level of elementary education in Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal, India. We have used both primary and secondary data in this present study. The primary data have been collected through a self-made interview schedule prepared for the head of the institution as well as with close observation of school environment, and interaction with the students, and members of the Self-Help Group (SHG) who are dedicated to cooking the mid-day meal at the kitchen room of the schools. In this study, we have taken 49 schools, covering both Primary and Upper-Primary schools situated in different parts of Purba Medinipur district of the Indian state of West Bengal. Among these 49 studied schools, 38 schools are Primary Schools, and 11 schools are Upper-Primary Schools in higher secondary school ambience. The data were collected from September to December 2023. The secondary data have been collected from research articles, government reports, websites etc. Then, the collected data have been analyzed qualitatively.

Figure 01: Types of Institutes Covered under the Study

Source : Primary Data

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The present study aims to identify the various facilities provided by schools to their learners, assess the progress of institutions in terms of infrastructural facilities at the elementary education level, and explore issues related to the cooked mid-day meal program at the elementary level of educational institutions in Purba Medinipur district, West Bengal. Below are the findings of the study, followed by necessary discussion:

- A) **Availability of Separate Head Master/ Head Teacher Room:** This study reveals that only 43% of schools have separate Headmaster or Head-Teacher rooms for regulating different administrative and academic works smoothly. In the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal, it is revealed from the present study that there are 57% of schools, where there are no separate Headmaster or Head-Teacher room. According to the provisions laid down in the Sarva Siksha Abhiyan Scheme, there should be a separate Headmaster or Head-Teacher room in every school. But, after 22 years of Sarva Siksha Abhiyan implementation, it has been seen that a major portion of elementary level schools in Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal (57%) have no separate Headmaster or Head-Teacher room for smooth functioning of academic and administrative works of the school.

Figure 02: Availability of Separate Headmaster / Head-Teacher Room

Source: Primary Data

- B) **School Having Boundary Wall:** There are 57% of schools in Purba Medinipur district where boundary walls exist, but 43% of schools have no boundary wall. As per the provisions laid down in the Right to Education Act- 2009, each school should have a boundary wall as a safety measure for children. In Sarva Siksha Abhiyan, each school should have got the fund allocation for constructing proper boundary walls, but till now 43% of schools run without boundary walls in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal.

Figure 03: School Having Boundary Wall

Source: Primary Data

C) Status of Ramp with Handle: We have collected data regarding Ramp with Handle, which is a very important part of every school infrastructure mainly for the Children with Special Needs (CWSN). Through the Sarva Siksha Abhiyan Scheme, every school should have the funds to construct a Ramp with a Handle. After making various efforts regarding the construction of a ramp with a handle in the school building, it has been seen that there are 10% of schools in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal, where no ramp with a handle has been found. The majority of the schools (90%), have ramps with handle exist in the school building in the said district.

Figure 04: Status of Ramp with Handle

Source: Primary Data

D) Availability of Library : The study revealed that 22% of schools in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal had no library, while 78% of the schools surveyed did have a library.

Figure 05: Availability of Library in School

Source: Primary Data

- E) **Availability of Electricity:** All the schools under the study have an electricity connection, and they use it fully for running fans and lighting the bulb in the classroom.

Figure 06: Availability of Electricity

Source: Primary Data

- F) **School Having Playground:** The playground is an important part of the school. It has been revealed from the present study that 59% of schools in the Purba Medinipur district have playgrounds, though 41% of schools have no playgrounds.

Figure 07: School Having Playground

Source: Primary Data

- G) **Availability of Tap-Water:** In the Purba Medinipur district, there are 90% of schools where tap-water is available, but 10% of schools where students drink water from tube wells.

Figure 08: Availability of Tap-Water

Source: Primary Data

- H) **Quality of Drinking-Water:** When we asked the head of the institute regarding the quality of drinking water, 92% of the heads of the institute responded that the quality of drinking water is purely safe. However, it is very alarming that 8% of the heads of the institute of elementary level schools in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal said that the available drinking water source of their school is not safe to drink.

Figure 09: Quality of Drinking-Water

Source: Primary Data

- I) **Status of Arsenic Test of Drinking Water:** When we asked the head of the institute regarding the arsenic test of the drinking water regularly, in response of that question, 59% of heads of the institute said that they had done the said test regularly, and 41% of heads of the institute said that they did not go through the arsenic test of their source of drink water. It is evident from the Government of West Bengal’s recent report made in 2021 that about 78.1% arsenic contaminations have been found in the Purba Medinipur district (<https://phed.sunandainternational.org/dash-new/purba-medinipur>). Therefore, it can be concluded that the district is highly vulnerable to arsenic contamination in drinking water. It is especially concerning that 41% of schools in the Purba Medinipur district have not undergone testing for arsenic in their drinking water sources.

Figure 10: Status of Arsenic Test on Regular Basis

Source: Primary Data

J) Toilet Facilities in School: It has been revealed from the study that 100% of schools have well-equipped and functioning boys' toilet for male students, whereas 98% of schools have well-equipped and functioning girls' toilet for female students; 2% of schools where no separate girls' toilets exist though those schools are co-educational i.e. both male and female students enroll every year. In 84% of schools separate staff toilets have been found, whereas in 16% of schools where no separate staff toilets exist. When we asked the head of the institute regarding the regular cleanliness of the school's toilets, in response to that 92% head of the institute said that they cleaned the toilet regularly, whereas 8% head of the institute said that regular cleaning could not be done.

Table 01: Toilet Facilities in Elementary Level Schools of Purba Medinipur District

Boys Students' Toilet		Girls Students' Toilet		Staff Toilet		Clean Everyday	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
100%	NIL	98%	2%	84%	16%	92%	8%

Source: Primary Data

K) Status of Cooked Mid-Day Meal Programme in Purba Medinipur District:
 It has been revealed from the present study that 100% of schools in the Purba Medinipur district of the Indian state of West Bengal have well-equipped kitchen rooms for their Cooked Mid Day Meal Programme (CMDMP). 94% Elementary level of Educational institutes in the Purba Medinipur district have well-equipped storerooms for their Cooked Mid Day Meal Programme, whereas it has been found from the present study that 6% of schools have no storeroom for their Cooked Mid Day Meal Programme. Making a 'kitchen garden' in the school premises is one of the good practices regarding Cooked Mid-Day Meal Programme implementation. We observed during our field visit that 53% of schools have made a kitchen garden in their school premises, where they produced seasonal vegetables without applying chemicals like fertilizers, pesticides etc. and cooked those in their school's Mid Day meal; whereas we did not find kitchen garden in 47% schools' premises. For safety purposes, in schools where Mid Day meals run, there should be a provision of having at least one fire extinguisher in the kitchen room laid down in the Sarva Siksha Abhiyan scheme. We observed during our field visit that 69% of schools have functioning fire extinguishers in their kitchen room, whereas in 31% of schools, we did not find any fire extinguishers in their kitchen room or on their school premises. During our field visit, we observed that 29% of schools have cooked their Mid Day with Liquefied Petroleum Gas (L.P.G.); 53% of schools have cooked their Mid Day with wood, and 18% schools have used both L.P.G. and wood for cooking their Mid Day.

Table 02: Status of Cooked Mid-Day Meal Programme in Elementary Level Schools of Purba Medinipur District

Kitchen Room		Store Room		Kitchen Garden		Fire Extinguisher		Fuel Used for CMDMP		
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	L.P.G.	Wood	Both Wood & L.P.G.
100%	NIL	94%	6%	53%	47%	69%	31%	29%	53%	18%

Source: Primary Data

KEY FINDINGS

The study conducted in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal highlights several critical infrastructural and administrative aspects of elementary schools.

Notably, only 43% of schools had a separate room for the Headmaster or Head-Teacher, while 57% lacked this basic facility.

Similarly, 57% of schools had boundary walls, leaving 43% without adequate campus security.

In terms of accessibility, 90% of schools had ramps with handles, although 10% did not, indicating gaps in inclusive infrastructure.

Library facilities were available in 78% of schools, while 22% lacked them.

Electricity was universally available, supporting lighting and fans in the classrooms.

A total of 59% of schools had playgrounds, leaving 41% without such spaces for physical activities.

Drinking water facilities were largely satisfactory, with 90% relying on tap water and 92% of school heads affirming its safety, although 8% admitted the water was unsafe. Notably, 41% of schools had not tested their water sources for arsenic.

Toilet facilities were nearly universal for boys (100%) and girls (98%), although 2% of co-educational schools lacked separate toilets for girls. Staff toilets were present in 84% of schools. Regular toilet cleaning was reported by 92% of heads.

All schools had functional kitchens for the Mid-Day Meal Programme, and 94% had storerooms, while 6% lacked storage. Kitchen gardens were present in 53% of schools. Fire safety measures were found in 69% of schools, but 31% lacked fire extinguishers. Cooking methods varied: 29% used LPG, 53% used wood, and 18% used both.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the infrastructural and environmental gaps identified, several key recommendations are proposed to enhance the overall educational experience in Purba Medinipur district schools.

First, all schools should establish designated administrative spaces, as over half currently lack such facilities, hindering effective management. Constructing boundary walls for the 43% of schools without them is essential for ensuring campus security. To support inclusivity, ramps with handrails must be installed in the 10% of schools where they are missing, complying with accessibility norms.

Library facilities should be provided in the 22% of schools currently without them to enrich learning resources.

Playgrounds must also be developed for the 41% of schools lacking outdoor recreational areas.

Immediate attention is required for the 8% of schools with unsafe drinking water, along with mandatory and regular arsenic testing in the 41% of schools that neglect this. Gender-sensitive infrastructure must be improved by building girls' toilets in the remaining 2% of coeducational schools and ensuring staff toilets in all institutions. Sanitation standards can be raised by enforcing regular cleaning in the 8% of schools not doing so.

To strengthen fire safety, extinguishers should be installed in the 31% of schools currently without them, particularly in kitchens. Transitioning schools from wood-based cooking to cleaner LPG alternatives is vital, as over half still rely on wood.

Schools lacking kitchen storerooms (6%) should be equipped accordingly to preserve food hygiene, while promoting kitchen gardens in the 47% of schools without them can support nutrition and sustainability.

Training programs for cooking staff and regular infrastructure and hygiene audits should be implemented to ensure continuous safety, health, and quality improvements.

These measures, collectively, aim to foster a more inclusive, secure, and developmentally supportive school environment across the district.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study draw attention to several essential infrastructural and resource-related challenges faced by schools in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal. While noteworthy progress has been made in providing basic facilities such as functioning toilets, electricity, and kitchen rooms for the cooked mid-day meal programme, there stay behind some essential deficiencies that must be addressed to guarantee an equitable and beneficial learning environment for all students.

Issues like having separate administrative room for headmasters, few boundary walls, few library resources, and few playgrounds show the necessary requirement for infrastructure modernization in some schools across the district. Despite the fact that most of the schools have ramps with handle it shows that there is some consideration of user-friendliness though a few schools still require such basic amenities for children with disabilities.

Of these, the hurdles observed in some schools in realizing hygiene and safety include the lack of safe source of drinking water, the absence of fire extinguishers and the absence of female-only toilets in some of the co-educational schools. It is also sad to find out that many

schools use charcoal or wood in preparing their cooked mid-day meal programme, the need to encourage schools to use cleaner and safe method of cooking such as LPG.

The study shows that while many schools in Purba Medinipur have met basic educational standards, there is still a need for targeted improvements, especially in the areas of sanitation, safety, and environmental sustainability. Addressing these gaps will be necessary to creating a more inclusive and caring environment for students and staff members.

Overall, the study supports the need for policymakers, educational stakeholders and local authorities to keep investing in school facilities and property. Only by paying persistent attention to those deficient areas can the district guarantee all students to get optimum safe, healthy, and total development which is academically and physically right.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, N. & Tripathi, P.K. (2024). Elementary Education of Purba Medinipur District of West Bengal: An Empirical Study. *Anwesa: A Journal of Education*, 16, 81-90.
- Burra, N. (2006). *Born Unfree: Child Labour, Education and the State in India*, New Delhi : Oxford University Press.
- Colclough, C. (1980). *Primary Schooling and Economic Development: A Review of the Evidence*. World Bank Staff Working Paper No 399, Washington DC, USA: World Bank.
- Das, A. (2007). How Far Have We Come in Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 42(1).
- Little, A.W. (2010). *Access to Elementary Education in India: Politics, Policies and Progress*, CREATE Research Monograph No. 44. University of Sussex : Centre for International Education, Department of Education.
- National Education Policy 2020, Retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf on December 27, 2023 at 22:52 IST.
- Proctor, A. (2001). *Learning to teach in the Primary Classroom*. London: Routledge.
- Report of the Education Commission (1964-66)*. New Delhi: Ministry of Education, Government of India. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/ReportOfTheEducationCommission1964-66D.S.KothariReport/page/n1/mode/2up> on November 25, 2024 at 22:47 IST.
- The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, Retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/RTE_Section_wise_rationale_rev_0.pdf on January 29, 2024 at 23:19 IST.

WEB REFERENCES

1. <https://phed.sunandainternational.org/dash-new/purba-medinipur>
2. <https://dmnorthwest.delhi.gov.in/scheme/sarva-shiksha-abhiyan/>